

The influence of rainwater composition on the conservation state of cementitious building materials

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ABSTRACT

Rainwater is one of main pollution tracer around the world. There are many reasons that can explain the presence and high concentrations of certain hazardous elements (HEs) in the rainwater (traffic, marine port activities, industry, etc.). In this work, rainwater samples were collected at six different locations in the Metropolitan Bilbao (Basque Country, north of Spain) during November 2014. HEs concentrations were determined by means of Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and anions by ion chromatography. The pH and redox potential values on these samples were also assessed. According to the obtained results, different trends along the estuary of Bilbao have been observed. To corroborate some hypothesis, thermodynamic simulations and correlation analyses were also carried out using quantitative data. These trends are closely related to the surrounding pollution and marine influence. Finally, in order to ascertain the influence of the Metropolitan Bilbao rainwater on buildings materials, a recent construction was characterized. Using techniques such as Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) and Raman Spectroscopy, different types of sulfates and nitrates were observed.

Keywords: Rainwater, wet depositions, ion chromatography, ICP-MS, Raman spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

Rainwater composition plays an important role in scavenging soluble components from the atmosphere and it can also help to understand the relative contributions of different kind of atmospheric pollutants (Wang and Han 2011). Although, more than 90% of the total amount of pollutants present in the atmosphere can be lixiviated by rainwater (Gromping et al. 1997), the rainwater itself can carries high concentrations of metals and metalloids among others cations and anions such as ammonium, nitrites, nitrates, sulfates, chlorides etc. Furthermore, the main environmental problem related with the rainwater composition is its acidification (add: Arenas-Lago et al., 2013; Cerqueira et al., 2011, 2012; Dias et al., 2014; Garcia et al., 2014; Hower et al., 2013; Kronbauer et al., 2013; Martinello et al., 2014; Ramos et al., 2015). Acid rain is usually formed due to dissolution of acid aerosols (mainly SO_x and NO_x) coming from anthropogenic sources. This acid rain supposes one of the major global environmental problems due to its important impact on vegetation and aquatic environments (Gromping et al. 1997). The deposition of acid rain on constructions has negative influence in the conservation state of the building materials used on them (Bravo et al. 2006). Since the 20th century, Europe has experienced a strong industrialization and an extensive road traffic, which affected strongly surrounded environment and subsequently also the rainwater composition. For this reason, it is important to characterize the anthropogenic pollutants which can change the original composition of the initial rainwater. In this way, different research groups have analyzed rainwater composition of different areas, using ion chromatography and Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), in forest areas with haze (Norela et al. 2013), semi-urban areas (Alahmr et al. 2012), rural areas (Zhang et al. 2011, Ostapczuk et al. 2002), and industrial areas (Ostapczuk et al. 2002). In this sense, many authors are trying to study the pollution levels based on the study of air composition, rainwater composition and depositions on geological samples (Attar 2013). Regarding rainwater analyses, they can be performed following different objectives. For example, depending of the air mass trajectories, the water vapor and subsequently rainwater can transport different compounds from biomass burning emissions during the pre-monsoon season like in Lijiang (China) (Zhang et al. 2014). Sometimes, it is necessary to know the composition of rainwater if the collected rainwater is used to drink (Malassa et al. 2014). In other cases, rainwater analyses can help to determine the presence of rare earth elements, as the study of Iwashita et al. in the suburban area of Tokyo (Iwashita et al. 2011). There are also some studies about concentrations of heavy metals such as Cu, Cd, Zn and Pb by means of potentiometric

stripping analyses (PSA) (Cerqueira et al. 2014). Other works, studied the variability of some anions in rainwater in Portugal by means of Ion Chromatography (Santos et al. 2011). In this way, the industrial activities have high influence in the ongoing process of atmospheric and rainwater chemistry alteration (Lara et al. 2001). Other works have focused their studies on the concentrations of anions, cations and pH variability in mountain areas without pollution (Niu et al. 2014). In addition, there are also studies about nitrogen fractions and soluble organic compounds in rainwater from marine environments (Gioda et al. 2008). Other studies focused their attention on the heavy metal concentration variability in the rainwater depending on the differences on air directions in coastal areas (Koulousaris et al. 2009). Moreover, other studies dealt with the differentiation of possible trends in rainwater hazardous elements (HEs) concentrations in areas influenced by marine aerosol against areas not influenced by it (Srinivas et al. 2012). It is also important to highlight the influence of industry (Ummugulsum and Kadir 2014, Jong-Myoung et al. 2010, Figueiredo et al. 2013) and maritime traffic (Minjiang et al. 2013, Muellerd et al. 2011, Contini et al. 2011) to understand the reasons of the presence of certain contaminants as well as the different concentration levels of heavy metals and airborne particulate matter in general (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), especially in areas influenced by industrial harbor activities.

In this work, rainwater samples from six different locations in Metropolitan Bilbao (Basque Country, north of Spain) during November 2014 were collected. HEs concentrations were determined by means of ICP-MS. Anions were quantified using the ion chromatography technique and pH and Redox potential values were also determined. Finally, in order to assess the influence of certain pollutants transported by the rainwater from Metropolitan Bilbao, different analyses on cementitious building materials from a construction located in the area of Metropolitan Bilbao (Berango, north of Spain) were conducted by means of Raman spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS).

2. Experimental

2.1 Sampling Locations

The sampling of rainwater on each location from Metropolitan Bilbao (Basque Country, north of Spain) was conducted at the same day (3rd November 2014) (see Figure 1).

The first sampling point was *El Arenal*, located in the heart of Bilbao and in the upper part of the estuary. This sampling point can provide information about the HEs and acid

aerosol level dissolved in rainwater in the heart of the city. Prior to these analyses, it is assumed that the high road traffic in this area can be a significant source of pollutants (e.g. airborne particulate matter (APM) and NO_x). Industrial activity should not have influence, because there is no industry that can contribute to increase the metallic particles and acid gases input.

The second sampling point was placed in *Deusto*, on the shore of the estuary. *Deusto* is also highly influenced by road traffic, like the *El Arenal* sampling area. The main difference with *El Arenal* sampling point is that *Deusto* can suffer diffuse influence of industrial activity, thus, this source can contribute to increase the APM and acid aerosol emissions.

The third sampling point chosen was *Zorroza*, on the banks of the estuary. In this area the main industrial activity of the Metropolitan Bilbao is located. These types of focal points can emit high concentration of acid gases and APM to the atmosphere. In contrast, road traffic should not be a pollutants emission source, because the number of vehicles in this area is minimal.

The fourth sampling point chosen for rainwater sampling was *Punta Begoña* in Getxo. Historically in this area high level of SO₂ emissions have been detected. The main pollutants emission source is the industrial port. Moreover, a high affluence of vehicles is registered in this area, because of the presence of Ereaga Beach and Algorta Sport Harbour.

The fifth sampling point chosen was a residential area in *Berango*. This area is located relatively close to the coast (2 km) and could also experiments the influence of diffuse marine aerosol and road traffic.

Finally the sixth sampling point chosen was the *Fortress of La Galea*, which is located in an area with low road traffic, but with a clear influence of the marine environment and the industrial port. Moreover the emissions from a petroleum refinery, a power generation plant producing liquid hydrocarbures as fuel and from the maritime traffic of the Bay of Abra (Port of Bilbao) increase the pollutants concentration levels in the rainwater of this area.

2.2 Material and sampling

All the rainwater samples from the six sampling points were collected using 2 litres PYREX[®] glass beaker (The Science Company, Denver, USA) and 800 ml SCHOTT

DURAN glass beaker (DURAN Group GmbH, Wertheim/Main, Germany). Before the sampling, the new glass baketers were rinsed with Milli-Q water, in order to ensure the cleanliness of each container. After sampling, rainwater samples were filtered using 20ml BRAUN Omnifix® syringe and a MN Chromafil® Xtra PA-45/25 filter with 0.45 µm of pore size and 25 mm of diameter.

For the Berango cementitious building materials, the sampling was carried out using a little hammer, a chisel and scalpel. The average size of the extracted fragments never exceeded 2-3 cm² (in some cases, the size of the sample was lower).

2.3 Instrumentation

For the analysis of pH and redox potential of the rainwater samples, Crison microph 2000 (Crison Instruments S.A. Alella, Barcelona, Spain) instrument was used. Please delete this part.

The quantification of metals and metalloids in rainwater samples was performed by means of an ICP-MS (NexION 300, Perkin Elmer) instrument in a class 100 clean room. The argon used was supplied by Praxair (99.995%, Madrid, Spain). Calibration standards were prepared by weight using an analytical balance model Mettler-Toledo XS205 (Colombus, OH, USA) with an accuracy of ± 0.00001 g from commercial solutions of 1000 mg/L supplied by Alfa Aesar (Specpure®, Plasma standard solution, Germany). Sc, Ge, In, Re and Bi were used as internal standards and the following isotopes ⁷Li, ¹⁰⁷Ag, ²⁷Al, ⁴⁴Ca, ⁸⁸Sr, ⁹⁸Mo, ¹¹⁴Cd, ¹²⁰Sn, ¹²¹Sb, ¹³⁸Ba, ¹⁸⁴W, ²⁰²Hg and ²⁰⁶⁺²⁰⁷⁺²⁰⁸Pb were determined in standard mode and ²³Na, ²⁴Mg, ³⁹K, ⁴⁷Ti, ⁵¹V, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁵⁹Co, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶⁵Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁷⁵As, ⁷⁸Se, ¹¹¹Cd isotopes were determined using a collision cell and an He flow, in order to eliminate possible polyatomic interferences.

Moreover, soluble salts analysis in rainwater samples was carried out using a Dionex ICS 2500 ion chromatograph connected to a conductimetric detector (ED50 Dionex conductimetric detector) with post-column suppression (Dionex Corporation, Sunnyvale, California, USA). The anions quantified were F⁻, Cl⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻. For their separation, an Ion Pac AS11-HC (4x250 mm) column and anionic postcolumn Ion Pac GS11-HC (4x50mm) were used. As mobile phase 20mM Na₂CO₃-NaHCO₃ solution, 1.5 ml/min flow and 112mA of supresion voltage was used. The data adquisition and integration were carried out using Chromaleon 6.60-SPIa software (Dionex Corporation, Sunnyvale, California, USA).

For the molecular characterization of cementitious materials from Berango building, two Raman spectrometers were employed. Firstly, a portable spectrometer for the in situ or field analyses in which the materials preliminary screening without being removed from the façade was used. After the preliminary analyses, samples were extracted in order to be measured using a benchtop spectrometer for an in-depth study, to identify the maximum number of compounds on each sample. The portable Raman spectrometer used was an innoRam™ model (B&WTEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA) which implements a 785 nm excitation laser and it has a maximum output power of 300 mW. Variable attenuation of the output power was achieved through the implementation of filters, which allowed for the reduction of the output power down to 1% of the maximum. The spectra were typically collected using a wavelength range of 100–2200 cm⁻¹, although in some measurements larger ranges were collected. The measurement time for each spectrum ranged from 1 to 10 s, and two to twenty repeated acquisitions were averaged to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The Raman probe (down to 0.1 mm focal spot size) can be operated by hand or mounted on a micro-video camera to reduce the spot size.

The Raman measurements in the laboratory were carried out using a Renishaw RA100 Raman spectrometer (Renishaw, Gloucestershire, UK), which also includes a 785 nm excitation laser. The microscopic analyses were performed using 20x and 50x long-range objective lenses mounted in the video-camera where the Raman probe was connected. The spectra were typically collected from 100 to 3000 cm⁻¹, although larger wavelength ranges were also employed in some of the measurements. The exposure time for each spectrum ranged from 1 to 10 s, and ten to seventy repeated acquisitions were averaged to increase the signal-to-noise ratio. In this case also, the laser power was attenuated to avoid thermal decomposition of the sample. Both Raman instruments were calibrated daily using the 520 cm⁻¹ Raman band of a crystalline silicon chip. Spectral acquisition with the innoRam™ and RA100 spectrometers were performed using the BWSpec™ 3.26 (B&WTEK_{INC.}) and the Renishaw Wire 3.2 software packages respectively. The Raman data were interpreted by comparing the acquired spectra with the spectra of pure standard compounds obtained from the e-VISNICH dispersive Raman database, which contains Raman spectra of natural, industrial and cultural heritage compounds, following a methodology described elsewhere (Maguregui et al. 2010). Open access Raman spectral databases (e.g., RRUFF (Downs and Hall-Wallace 2002)) were also used to assign some of the Raman bands. The spectral interpretation and data treatment were carried out using the GRAMS/AI 7.02 software package (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, USA).

The SEM-EDS analyses were carried out using a EVO[®]40 Scanning Electron Microscope (Carl Zeiss NTS GmbH, Germany) coupled to an X-Max Energy-Dispersive X-Ray spectrometer (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom) for electron image acquisitions and elemental analysis (punctual and imaging). Although sometimes cementitious materials alone are not conductive, it was possible to acceptable optimal results without carbon or gold coating. The SEM images were obtained at high vacuum employing an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and a 10–400 μm working distance. Different magnifications (reaching up to $\times 6,800$) were used for secondary electron images and an integration time of 50 s was employed to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The EDS spectra were acquired and treated using the INCA software. Similar procedures were previously reported (Cutruneo et al., 2014; Oliveira et al., 2012a,b; Quispe et al., 2012; Ribeiro et al., 2010, 2013; Saikia et al., 2014, 2015; Silva et al., 2012).

3. Results

The obtained pH and Redox potential values for the six sampling points are shown in Table 1.

The carbon dioxide (CO_2) concentration on each sampling points should be constant, thus we should not expect pH variations among the sampling points. Unless basic particulate matter reacts with the rainwaters, the pH can vary slightly due to the influence of other acid gases such as NO_x and SO_x , which when are dissolved in rainwater, they give rise to nitrates and sulfates respectively. As seen the pH is constant for three sampling points (Deusto, Berango, La Galea; $\text{pH} = 6.46 \pm 0.5$) (see also Figure 2). Only the most urban influenced sampling location has lower pH value. The differences in the pH values obtained, in Zorroza and Punta Begoña are due to the neutralization of the mentioned acids by the suspended particles. For example, in Punta Begoña the rainwater pH obtained was 7.12; this could be due to such neutralization processes between the carbonate particulate matter emitted during the maritime port activity.

The redox potential values show a lower redox potential in the estuary area, in comparison to the most outer sampling points (Berango and La Galea). This could have a relationship with the road traffic and the industrial activities. In these areas, the ozone concentration is influenced by the higher volume of road traffic, responsible of NO_x and VOC gases emissions and industrial emissions. In this sense, when the sampling point is further from the city (Punta Begoña), the ozone concentration would be lower and thus,

the reduction potential of that area will be reduced, which is what it is observed in the analysis of collected rainwater samples.

3.1. Metals and metalloids concentrations in rainwater samples

The analysis of metals and metalloids in the atmosphere is of great interest, as certain HEs such as lead, nickel, cadmium and arsenic (pay attention, As is not metal) are common air pollutants which are mainly emitted by some industrial activities and during the burning of coal. Although their level in the environment is low, their deposition can cause serious consequences, such as their influence on the degradation of specific building materials included in constructions (ok, but who?) add more explanation, please.

In this work, the concentrations of each HEs on each rainwater sample are presented as an average of three repetitive measurements on each sample (see the concentrations in Table S1 of Supplementary Material). The Sr and Cu concentrations increase slightly or remain practically constant, while the rainwater analyzed is close to the coast. As can be seen in Figure 3, the highest Sr concentration was identified in Punta Begoña rainwater. Both elements, Cu and Sr could have their origin in the port activity near the area. Marine aerosol can also contribute to increase the Sr concentration in rainwater (Culkin 1965).

Regarding lithium, the sampling point where a maximum concentration was obtained was Punta Begoña. It is necessary to highlight that the concentration of Li for La Galea rainwater in the Figure 2 was not included because a higher concentration comparing with other points (437 ppb) was obtained. This high value could be related with the impact of the port activity, which would also explain the maximum value obtained in Punta Begoña. For the Ag, As, Se and Co, low concentrations were detected. As can be seen in Figure 3, the concentrations of some of these HEs are especially high in the rainwater from Punta Begoña (As), Berango (Ag) and in the rainwater from La Galea (Se). The high presence of As in Punta Begoña rainwater, can be due to the influence of road traffic (Luilo et al. 2014), which is very high in this area. Regarding cobalt, the concentration in Zorroza and Berango is very similar. This can be due to the road traffic also (Obara et al. 2011).

For the case of Na, Mg, K and Ca, the highest concentrations were determined in the rainwater sample from Punta Begoña. Even higher concentrations of sodium were detected in La Galea rainwater, which like Punta Begoña, it also undergo the direct

influence of marine aerosol (located on a cliff in front of Bay of Abra). On the contrary, in the sampling points closer to Bilbao city center, the concentrations of sodium decrease (see Figure 3). The highest concentration of Ca was detected in Punta Begoña rainwater. Ca can be present in the atmosphere as calcium carbonate particles. This observation agrees with the neutralized pH determined in Punta Begoña rainwater, as an influence of a higher concentration of carbonates. As it has been mentioned before, this kind of particulate matter can come from the mineral phases transported from the port activity. Natural erosion and emission of calcareous stones from the surrounding location can also contribute to increase the calcium carbonate particles emitted in this area. Considering the correlation analysis performed with all the variables quantified in the rainwater samples, the correlation matrix has been calculated (see the results in Table S3 from Supplementary Material). In this sense, a high correlation between calcium and strontium (0.98) was determined, which is an indicative of the presence of calcium carbonate coming from a calcareous rock, which usually contains noticeable amounts of strontium. Therefore, the presence of calcium carbonate particles from the atmosphere in the rainwater is evident. Moreover, the calcium carbonate particles can react in the atmosphere with the acid SO_2 (as H_2SO_4 after its incorporation to the rainfall or due to the humidity influence) and the other acids giving soluble calcium and bicarbonate.

Other elements such as Ba and Zn (see Figure 3) reach high concentrations for Punta Begoña and La Galea rainwaters respectively. Although in Punta Begoña, a high number of vehicles is registered due to the diary affluence of tourist who visit the beach and sport harbor, probably these two metals come from the port activity.

The highest concentration of V and Mn has been detected in the rainwater from Zorroza. Although iron concentration is also high in this sampling point, the maximum concentration was registered in Punta Begoña. The high concentrations of V, Mn and Fe in Zorroza and Fe in Punta Begoña could be due to the emissions of these metals coming from a near company which produce rolled steel coils from scrap and prerduced iron operations. The highest concentration of V and Mn in Zorroza rather than in Punta Begoña could be explained because the wind direction is oriented to Zorroza, therefore the metallic particles can be transported to this sampling point. Considering the correlation analysis performed with all the variables quantified in the rainwater samples, the correlation matrix has been calculated (see the result in Table S3 from Supplementary Material). In this sense, the coincident source of V and Mn was also confirmed because a high correlation was identified between both metals (0.93). In

Punta Begoña rainwater, higher concentrations of Fe were quantified due to the Fe emissions as a consequence of the fuel oil combustion from ships which enter and leave the Bilbao Port (Sorooshian et al. 2013).

Regarding Al and Ni, varying concentrations depending on the sampling area were observed. In Punta Begoña and El Arenal rainwater, higher concentration of these metals is present.

As can be seen in Figure 3, Cr and Mo concentrations in rainwater from all the sampling points are low. In Punta Begoña 0.5 ppb for both metals was determined a relatively low concentration. In this point, we have to highlight that for the case of La Galea, it was decided not to include in the bar chart because the concentrations of Cr and Mo were much higher than in the rest of sampling point (see Table S1 of Supplementary Material). The higher concentration of both metals, in La Galea rainwater, could be due to the emissions coming from the port activity. Finally, the concentrations of Cd, Ti, Sb and Pb are quite low. The highest concentrations of Pb and Cd were registered in La Galea rainwater. This could be because of the surrounded industry and maritime traffic that are present in the Abra Bay.

3.2. Quantification of anions in rainwater samples

Figure 4 shows different bar charts representing the concentrations of each anion present in the six rainwater samples.

The analysis of chloride ion (Cl^-) mainly provides information about the influence of marine aerosol, because the sampling points on Metropolitan Bilbao are clearly influenced by the Cantabrian Sea. The marine aerosol, generated spontaneously, is formed when the wind strikes over the surface of the ocean waves. Then, small bubbles discharge liquid particles in the air. These particles are impulsed at high speed and they are incorporated into the flowing air mass (O'Dowd and de Leeuw 2007). The highest concentration of chlorides was registered in the Punta Begoña and La Galea rainwaters, which are the closest areas to the sea. Thus, due to their location, they are more exposed to sea spray. The other four sampling points show considerably lower chloride concentrations (see also Table S2 from Supplementary Material). These concentrations can be related with the chloride background which is maintained along the Nervion River (which varies depending on the day, season etc.). Regarding the correlation analysis (see Table S3 from Supplementary Material), a high correlation was obtained between chloride and sodium (0.97) and chloride and magnesium (0.98). These

observation points out that the main chlorides incorporated or lixiviated by the rainwater coming from marine aerosol are sodium and magnesium chlorides.

In view of the results of fluorides (see Figure 4), there is no clear trend in the observed results. As it can be seen, fluorides were detected in Zorroza and El Arenal rainwaters, while in Punta Begoña, La Galea and Deusto this anion was not detected.

The absence or presence of nitrite ions (NO_2^-) in rainwater indicates if the emitted nitrogen to the atmosphere has been totally oxidized or not. NO_x can be oxidized in the atmosphere, by the influence of ozone (O_3). In the NO_x (mainly as N_2O) emissions, the N is in +1 oxidation (N (I)) state. N_2O can be oxidized into nitrite (NO_2^-) in where N is in +3 oxidation state (N (III)). Finally, these nitrites can be oxidized to form nitrate ions (NO_3^-) in where N is in +5 oxidation state (N (V)). The presence of nitrites in rainwater indicates that all the nitrogen emitted into the atmosphere has not been completely oxidized. As we can see in Figure 4, nitrites only were detected in Punta Begoña, the sampling point outside from Bilbao city center. In the city center, higher concentrations of ozone can be registered. In Punta Begoña, the concentration of ozone is not so high, thus the entire emitted N (I) cannot be oxidized to nitrates. However, in all other areas, as they are located very near or in the city center, ozone (O_3) concentrations may be high enough so that all the NO_x emitted into the atmosphere is oxidized to nitrates.

Nitrates appear in all sampling areas where previously nitrites were not found (see Figure 4). However, in Punta Begoña, nitrates and nitrites were detected in the rainwater. Therefore, in this area, the emitted N (I), has been almost completely oxidized to N (V) (concentration of 1.4 ppm or 22.6 μM). However, a lower concentration (0.19 ppm or 4.13 μM) has not completely oxidized into N (V) and remains in the rainwater as Nitrogen (I) or nitrites. That is, the 12% of the total emitted N (I) is in the form of nitrite, and the remaining 88% is completely oxidized to nitrate. In order to understand this situation, a thermodynamic simulation of the described system (total nitrogen concentration of 27 μM) was done using the MEDUSA software (see Figure 5).

As seen, at the pH value (7.12) of the rainwater (see Figure 5), the major specie is NO_3^- , but NO_2^- is also present more or less in the same ratio observed experimentally in the rainwater. In this way, the thermodynamic simulation agrees with the experimental evidences.

Regarding the SO_x gases emissions to the atmosphere, SO₂ is the main gas emitted in where SO₂ can be oxidized to the +6 oxidation state to form sulfates. This oxidation process in +4 oxidation state can also take place due to ozone (O₃). As can be seen in Figure 4, the maximum sulfates concentrations were determined in Punta Begoña, La Galea and Zorroza sampling points, which are clearly influenced by industrial activity, as has been remarked throughout the manuscript.

For the case of Punta Begoña, these high concentrations are due to the SO₂ emissions coming from the port activity. In Zorroza, waste management companies can contribute to increase the SO₂ emissions which lead to sulfates. However Deusto, El Arenal and Berango, sulfates concentrations on rainwater are relatively low, as these areas are not exposed to any industrial activity, and therefore there is no a nearby source of SO₂ acid gas emissions. Apart from the SO₂ input coming from anthropogenic activities, natural sources can also contribute to increase the sulphur concentration in rainwater. Concretely, a high correlation (0.72) was found between sulfates and chloride anions (see Table S3 from Supplementary Material). This correlation could suggest that sulfates present in the rainwater can also come from the marine aerosol, like the chloride input.

3.3. Chemometric treatment of HEs and anions concentrations in rainwaters

In order to extract additional conclusions about the variability of the rainwater in the different sampling points, chemometric analyses based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were carried out with the HEs and anions concentrations in the rainwaters from the different sampling areas. These analyses were performed using the Unscrambler 7.2 software all the variables quantified in the rainwater samples.

In the score plot obtained after the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), three different groups can be observed (see Figure 6). The first one represents La Galea rainwater, a sampling point highly impact by the marine aerosol.

Having a look to the loadings plot, La Galea is defined by high concentrations of nitrates, sulfates, Mg, Na and Cl (see Figure 6). These anions and metalloids are the main components of the salts transported in the marine aerosol. This observation agrees with the correlation analysis results, because a high correlation was also determined between Na-Cl and Mg-Cl as it has been mentioned before. The sampling areas impacted by the urban-industrial emissions (El Arenal, Deusto, Zorroza and Berango)

are grouped together (see Figure 6 bottom). In this case, this group and the elements according to the loadings plots are characterized by a higher presence of Fe, F, Mn, Sb, Cu, Ti and V. Finally, a third group, representing the rainwater of Punta Begoña sampling location was defined (see Figure 6 bottom). In this case, the influence of the port activity can be clearly observed. As it has been mentioned before, nitrites (NO_2^-) were detected as well as metals such as As, Sr and Ba which their presence is also high as explained before (see loadings plot at the top of Figure 6).

3.4. Deposition of Airborne Particulate Matter and acid aerosols transported by rainwater and its influence on the conservation state of cementitious building materials

Considering the concentration of metals and anions from the rainwaters at each sampling point, Berango is one of the areas with fewer amounts of HEs and dissolved anions. However, different pathologies were identified in the building materials (artificial stone and bricks) from detached houses from this area (Morillas et al. 2015a). In this sense, in order to assess if the cementitious materials from another detached house of Berango, are suffering airborne particulate matter depositions and impact from the acid aerosols dissolved in the rainwater and deposited on the façades, a complete characterization of those materials has been conducted. In this sense, cementitious materials were taken from the façades oriented to the rainwater and wind direction.

3.5. Molecular characterization of Berango cementitious materials

Raman spectroscopy was useful to define different original compounds present on the original cementitious materials, such as hematite (Fe_2O_3 , Raman bands at 219, 237, 288, 403, 488 and 606 cm^{-1}), limonite ($\text{FeO}(\text{OH})\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Raman bands at 239, 298, 394 and 552 cm^{-1}) and quartz (SiO_2 , Raman bands at 262, 355, 394, 464, 695, 805 and 1159 cm^{-1}) (see Figure 7). These compounds act as additives in the cement setting (Chandra 1996). As we can see in Figure 7A, the Raman analyses of the efflorescence from cement material reveals the presence of thenardite (Na_2SO_4 , Raman bands at 450, 464, 620, 631, 646, 992, 1100, 1130 and 1151 cm^{-1}) and natrite (Na_2CO_3 , Raman bands at 194, 700 and 1080 cm^{-1}). The thenardite-mirabilite system ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is a common pathology in cementitious building materials (Morillas et al. 2013, Maguregui et al. 2012, Matovic et al. 2014). Apart from these compounds, a very dangerous compound which can appear in the cement materials was observed. This compound was the ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{SO}_4)_3\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Raman bands at 218, 361, 448, 544, 600, 648, 857, 890, 986 and 1061 cm^{-1}) (see Figure 7B). Prior to ettringite

formation, thaumasite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Si}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is usually formed. The thaumasite is formed in cements as a consequence of a continuous sulfation process. In the cement setting, the sulfates react with the cement compounds such as C3A (tricalcium aluminate) forming the ettringite and the hydrated calcium monosulphoaluminate ($\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{SO}_4) \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) consuming the added sulfates in form of additive (Bart et al. 2013). Nevertheless, ettringite can follow reacting with an excess of sulfates and with the carbonated cement in order to form the thaumasite. The formation of this compound give rise to the worst decay processes which can be find in the cement, because the presence of this compound promote volume changes causing the buiding wall collapse. Moreover if the thaumasite follow reacting with the hydrated calcium monosulphoaluminate, it can promote also the absolute loss of material (Sahu et al. 2002, Brocken and Nijland 2004).

As it is described in previous works, high quantities of sulfate compounds can appear in cementitious materials (Morillas et al. 2015a). The main sulfate usually identified on cementitious materials was the gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). In this sense, as we can see in Figure 7C, among rutile (TiO_2 , Raman bands at 448 and 609 cm^{-1}) and calcite (CaCO_3 , Raman bands at 280, 712 and 1086 cm^{-1}), gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, main Raman band at 1008 cm^{-1}) together with thenardite (Na_2SO_4 , main Raman band at 992 cm^{-1}) were identified. Apart from that, gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, with its main Raman band at 1008 cm^{-1}) was also identified together with calcite (CaCO_3 , with its main Raman band at 1086 cm^{-1}), adularia (KAlSi_3O_8 , Raman bands at 285, 473 and 512 cm^{-1}) and nitratine (NaNO_3 , Raman band at 190, 724, 1067 and 1384 cm^{-1}). The presence of nitratine on cementitious materials can suggests a continuous attack of nitrates (Morillas et al. 2012), since nitrate salts are very soluble and sometimes difficult to identify its presence. Although the concentration of nitrates in the rainwater from Berango was low, the presence of nitratine could be a signal of possible wet depositions of NO_x coming from the atmosphere. Additionally, a possible nitrate salts input coming from infiltration waters cannot be rejected.

3.6. Elemental characterization of Berango cementitious materials

In order to complement the analyses carried out in cementitious materials by Raman spectroscopy, SEM-EDS point by point and imaging analyses were carried out. An example of these analyses is presented in Figure 8. Nitrogen was identified on the cementitious materials in more than 10 spectra (see Figure 8A and B). This observation can be related with the possible presence of nitrates, such as nitratine (NaNO_3) which

was identified by Raman spectroscopy as it has been mentioned in the previous section. Sodium nitrate can be present in the building material as particulate matter coming from the salts included in the marine aerosol (see Figures 8A and 8B) (Gupta et al. 2015) or can be formed in the material starting from the sodium carbonate in reaction with nitrate salts input coming from infiltration waters.

Among the nitrogen, other elements related also with the marine aerosol influence such as Cl were detected by EDS. Although Berango is not located next to the sea, the diffuse influence of the near marine environment is evident. Other elements such as sulphur and calcium, which could be related with the presence of some sulfate such as gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) which was also distinguished by Raman spectroscopy, were also identified by EDS. Moreover, the presence of K, Al, Si and O in EDS spectra, can be related with the presence of potassium aluminosilicates (e.g. KA_3SiO_8) which were also identified by Raman spectroscopy. This kind of silicates can be original compounds of the cementitious material itself, but they can also be related with particulate matter depositions. Finally, the presence of Fe in the EDS spectra could be related with the different iron oxides used as additives in the characterized cementitious material, but their signal can also come from iron particles deposited on the surface of the cementitious materials.

Other microscopic areas from cementitious materials surface show the presence of K, Na, S and O (see Figure 8C). Considering that Cl was not present in the EDS spectrum, it cannot be said that NaCl is present in this microscopic area. Therefore, the most probable compound that could be present is a Aphthitalite ($\text{K}_3\text{Na}(\text{SO}_4)_2$). This compound was previously identified in efflorescences from cementitious materials (Matovic et al. 2010). The formation of these types of double sulfate compounds could be related with a continuous sulfation process (Morillas et al. 2015b). In this sense, although the concentration of sulfates in Berango rainwater was relatively low, a continuous deposition process of the acidified rainwater on the cementitious material can promote the formation of this type of compounds.

Apart from point-by-point EDS analyses, mappings were also acquired on different microscopic areas from the cementitious material (see Figure 9). In the mapping shown in Figure 9, a clear distribution of NaCl can be observed, showing again the clear influence of marine aerosol. Apart from the halite (NaCl) presence, fluor was also detected, distributed in different microscopic areas and not as punctual depositions (see

Figure 9). This observation agrees with the data from Berango rainwater, where fluoride was the highest one among the six sampling points.

Apart from that, elements like Ca, Al, S, O follow the same distribution in the EDS maps (see Figure 9). This could suggest a possible presence of ettringite $\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$, also detected by Raman spectroscopy. Moreover, the presence of quartz (SiO_2) and adularia (KAl_3SiO_8) can be also distinguished at sight of the EDS mapping results (see Figure 9). Finally, remark the clear correlation between the distribution of S, O and Ca. This elemental distribution could be related to the presence of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), a compound identified also by Raman spectroscopic analyses.

4. Conclusions

The results presented in this work show a high variability of metals, metalloids and anions concentrations among the six rainwater samples taken from different points inside Metropolitan Bilbao. In general terms, the acidity of the samples increases while we are approaching to the Bilbao city center, due to the higher presence of acid gases dissolved in the rainwaters and originated from the influence of road traffic and industrial emissions. The reduced presence of particulate matter promotes the rainwater neutralization. Moreover, taking into account the results obtained by ICP-MS, the heavy metals concentrations reveal an influence of the surrounded industry and maritime port. The road traffic has also a clear influence. For the anions results quantified by ion chromatography, they revealed the influence of marine aerosol (mainly chlorides and fluorides in some cases) and green houses acid gases (presence of sulfates, nitrates and nitrites).

The influence of the acid compounds and metals transported in the rainwater which can be deposited on the surface of the buildings was evaluated in a specific sampling point, Berango, where apart from rainwater, cementitious materials from a modern house were characterized, in order to extract conclusions about the influence of the rainwater composition on the conservation state of such building materials. Although the rainwater from Berango showed the lowest concentration of anions, metals and metalloids, a clear impact of acid pollutants and metallic airborne particulate matter that can be transported by rainwater and deposited on building materials is evident.

Therefore, the combined use of a molecular microscopic technique (Raman spectroscopy) and elemental technique (SEM-EDS) demonstrate that the building, placed in a diffuse marine and diffuse urban-industrial environment such as Berango

area, can experiment a negative influence of acid aerosol and airborne particulate matter transported by rainwater in its conservation state. Thanks to Raman spectroscopy, it was possible to determine the presence of sulfate compounds such as ettringite, thenardite and gypsum which can be formed due to the sulfate input of the material itself, but also as an influence of SO_x wet depositions. Nitratine (NaNO₃) salt was also identified and its presence was reinforced with the N detection by means of EDS. This salt can be present on the cementitious materials as a dry deposition (airborne particulate matter coming from the marine aerosol).

SEM-EDS analyses (point by point and imaging) also revealed a clear influence of marine aerosol thanks to the identification of NaCl, the main salt transported by marine aerosol. Sulfate salts identified also by Raman spectroscopy (e.g. gypsum, thenardite, aphanitic and ettringite) was corroborated also by this elemental technique.

The whole multianalytical methodology described in this work have allowed to understand the high influence of acid aerosols and metal and metalloids transported in the rainwater on the conservation state of cementitious building materials. Metals, metalloids and acid aerosols can be deposited on the surface of these materials following dry and wet depositions. Airborne particulate matter (e.g. calcium carbonate) can also react with the acid aerosols in the atmosphere promoting the formation of secondary particles (e.g. transformation of calcium carbonate particles in reaction with the acid form of the SO₂ aerosol included in the rainwater forming calcium sulfate as secondary particle). These particles, together with the primary ones can be also deposited on the materials following a dry deposition.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. Sampling locations from Metropolitan Bilbao.

Figure 2. pH and Redox Potential tendency along the six analyzed rainwater samples.

Figure 3. Bar charts showing metals and metalloids concentrations (ng/g units) on each rainwater sample

Figure 4. Bar charts showing the anions concentrations (mg/L units) in the rainwater from each sampling points.

Figure 5. Thermodynamic modelling of the $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ system which takes place in the rainwater from Punta Begoña sampling point.

Figure 6. Scores (bottom) and loadings plots (top) obtained after the PCA analysis of the anions, metals and metalloids concentrations in rainwaters.

Figure 7. A) Raman spectrum showing the presence of thenardite (Na_2SO_4) and natrite (Na_2CO_3); B) Raman spectrum of ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$); C) Raman spectrum showing the presence of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), calcite (CaCO_3), thenardite

(Na_2SO_4) and rutile (TiO_2) and D) Raman spectrum showing the presence of adularia (KAlSi_3O_8), calcite (CaCO_3), gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and nitratine (NaNO_3).

Figure 8. A microphotograph of the cementitious material acquired using the SEM (left) and different EDS spectra of different points inside this microscopic area (right).

Figure 9. SEM-EDS mapping of cementitious building materials from a building in Berango.

pe = 7.60

$[\text{NO}_3^-]_{\text{TOT}} = 27.00 \mu\text{M}$

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

50 μm

TABLES

Table 1. pH and Redox potential values from each rainwater sample.

Sampling Points	pH	Redox Potential (mV)
El Arenal	6.20 ± 0.03	182 ± 1
Deusto	6.50 ± 0.03	172 ± 2
Zorroza	6.85 ± 0.03	167 ± 1
Punta Begoña	7.12 ± 0.02	166 ± 2
Berango	6.45 ± 0.03	299 ± 2
La Galea	6.43 ± 0.03	322 ± 2